

Twinn4MicroUp

Twining Innovation Hub for Microbial Platforms in Plastic Upcycling

D4.1 Report on Grant Proposal and Patent Application Trainings

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TwInn4MicroUp

Twinning Innovation Hub for Microbial Platforms in Plastic Upcycling

National Technical
University of Athens

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI DI BARI
ALDO MORO

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Partners

NTUA: Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (National Technical University of Athens)

TUS: Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest

IMGGE: Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade

UNIBA: Universita Degli Studi Di Bari Aldo Moro

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1. Executive Summary

The present document reports an overview of the training activities conducted and planned within the TwInn4MicroUp project to enhance the capacity of partner institutions—particularly the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)—in grant proposal development and patent application procedures. The report details the consortium’s strategy to strengthen research management, increase competitiveness in securing Horizon Europe funding, and promote effective protection of intellectual property. During the first ten months of the project, a series of targeted workshops, seminars, and mentorship sessions were organized by partners, including IMGGE, TUS, UNIBA, and NTUA. These activities focused on practical skills for grant writing, project planning, budgeting, and the patenting process. The training approach prioritized quality and direct applicability, ensuring that staff could immediately utilize new knowledge in active proposal submissions and project management tasks. Looking forward, the project will further strengthen NTUA’s research management and innovation capabilities through the organization of further seminars and the establishment of a dedicated Research Management and Administration (RMA) Office for EU funding. The upcoming period will also see continued collaboration with TUS and IMGGE to deliver specialized workshops on patent applications, ensuring NTUA staff are equipped with advanced skills in intellectual property protection. By drawing on the collective expertise of all partner organizations and focusing on practical, needs-based training, TwInn4MicroUp is laying a strong foundation for sustainable growth in research excellence and innovation impact.

2. Project Overview

TwInn4MicroUp is a three-year project funded by the EU Horizon Europe HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02, which started in September 2024. It involves four partners of which three from EU countries (Greece, Ireland and Italy) and one Associated Country (Serbia), all research institutions. The primary objective of the TwInn4MicroUp project is to significantly enhance the competitiveness and capabilities of NTUA in the areas of Project Management and Administration, Budget Acquisition, and Synthetic Microbial Biotechnology research. This enhancement aims to elevate NTUA’s research profile, contributing to the advancement of European socioeconomic goals. TwInn4MicroUp aims to introduce an innovative approach to upcycling plastic waste by

utilizing green biological/mechanical/chemical technologies to recover plastic monomers. This project will leverage modern molecular techniques to develop microbial cell factories that can produce bioactive compounds from plastic-derived feedstocks. This advancement has the potential to transform industries related to bio-colorants, biotherapeutics, bio-nutraceuticals, biosurfactants, and biomaterials.

3. Grant Proposal Trainings

As part of its strategic objective to strengthen research and administrative capacities, the Twinn4MicroUp project has planned a series of training activities focused on grant proposal development and patent applications. Recognising the importance of building a strong foundation in research management and innovation strategy, the project has prioritized participation in high-quality training programmes. These trainings are intended to support the preparation of competitive Horizon Europe proposals, improve financial and administrative coordination, and enable protection of research outputs through effective IP and patent strategies.

The project's training activities are designed to be both impactful and practical, focusing on the most pressing requirements for research management and innovation strategy. By prioritizing mentorship, targeted workshops, and hands-on support, the Twinn4MicroUp project ensures that the participant staff acquire essential skills in grant writing, patent application, and administrative management without overloading participants with repetitive seminars. This approach allows staff to immediately apply what they learn to ongoing proposal submissions and project coordination, maximizing the practical benefits of each training session.

While the number of formal seminars and workshops held to date may appear limited, this approach was carefully considered, in light of the partners' active engagement in preparing and submitting a substantial volume of grant proposals. As detailed in Chapter 4 (*Submitted Proposals*), the consortium has been highly involved in proposal development, reflecting the institutions' strong commitment to securing research funding. The high volume of proposals submitted has naturally shaped the project's training strategy, ensuring that capacity-building efforts are targeted and responsive to real-world needs.

Looking ahead, the project will continue to strengthen the research management capabilities of NTUA, leading to the establishment of a dedicated Research Management and Administration

(RMA) unit for national and EU funding (also see upcoming *Deliverable 4.2*). This specialized unit, to be developed in close collaboration with TUS, will streamline administrative processes, improve compliance, and support the institution's long-term goals for research excellence and innovation. By leveraging the expertise of partner institutions and tailoring training to the evolving needs of NTUA, the Twinn4MicroUp project is building a robust foundation for sustainable research management and successful EU project participation.

3.1 Performed Trainings

This chapter provides a structured overview of all relevant trainings attended by members of the Twinn4MicroUp consortium. It includes both internal and external programmes related to grant proposal development and patent application procedures. The following sections provide a structured overview of all relevant trainings attended by members of the Twinn4MicroUp consortium. This structure highlights the active involvement of all partners in strengthening project-relevant competencies. Where applicable, training content, materials, and key insights are summarised to demonstrate their relevance and potential impact on the implementation and long-term success of Twinn4MicroUp.

3.1.1 IMGGE partner

1| Training Title: **Horizon Europe Project Development, Proposal Writing and Project Implementation**

Organizer: European Training Academy - EUTA

Date: 18th November 2024

Location: Belgrade, Serbia

Consortium Participant(s): Ivana Aleksić

Ivana Aleksić attended a comprehensive five-day training organized by EUTA, one of the leading regional agencies specializing in EU project development and management. The program was structured into two modules: (i) **Module 1:** Preparation and writing of Horizon Europe proposals (*Days 1–2*), and (ii) **Module 2:** Budgeting and implementation of Horizon Europe projects (*Days 3–5*). The training was designed to cover all phases of the project lifecycle—from analysing Horizon Europe Work Programmes and open calls, through developing and writing project

proposals, to preparing budgets and managing funded projects. Practical sessions included work with actual application templates and evaluation forms, as well as analysis of relevant 2024/25 Horizon Europe calls. The training was led by a team of experienced professionals:

- *Day 1 & 4:* Dr Goran Stojanović (Full professor at the Faculty of Technical Sciences (FTS), University of Novi Sad (UNS), Serbia)– focus on structure and logic of project proposals, consortium building, and impact pathways.
- *Day 2:* Gordana Vlahović (International Relations Office, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad) – deep dive into Excellence and Impact sections, with detailed analysis of evaluation criteria
- *Day 3:* Dr Steve Quarrie (Head of Education and Training at EUTA – budgeting strategies, project coordination, and risk management from a project coordinator’s perspective.
- *Day 5:* Marija Šola Spasić – administrative and financial implementation of EU projects, with practical tips for grant holders.

The training was attended by 24 participants from various scientific research institutions in Serbia. Dr Aleksić received all relevant training materials and presentations, which will be made available to the project team.

Figure 1. Material from the “Horizon Europe Project Development, Proposal Writing and Project Implementation” training (IMGGE partner; Training No1).

2| Training Title: Horizon Europe Excellence Hubs Proposal Writing

Organizer: EUTA Training Agency

Date: 14th December 2024

Location: Belgrade, Serbia

Consortium Participant(s): Ivana Aleksić

This one-day training provided focused guidance on preparing competitive proposals for the Horizon Europe Excellence Hubs calls. Led by Prof. Dr Vesna Mandić (Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac)—an experienced Horizon Europe project writer and evaluator—the session offered participants clear, practice-oriented insights into what the European Commission expects from proposals submitted under this instrument.

Key topics covered included: (i) the specific objectives and structure of the Excellence Hubs calls, (ii) the distinction between different Excellence Hubs funding opportunities, and (iii) the

interpretation of evaluation criteria and common challenges and strategic approaches to proposal development. The training was attended by 19 participants from different scientific and research institutions in Serbia. Dr Aleksić received valuable guidance on aligning project concepts with policy priorities and regional innovation strategies. The training also addressed key elements of consortium composition, stakeholder involvement, and impact planning. All training materials, including presentation slides, were provided and will serve as references for future proposal planning.

Figure 2. Material from the “Horizon Europe Excellence Hubs Proposal Writing” training (IMGGE partner; Training No2).

3) Training Title: MSCA Staff Exchange

Organizer: IMGGE, University of Belgrade

Date: 7th December 2024

Location: Belgrade, Serbia

Consortium Participant(s): Ivana Aleksić, Jelena Simić, Jelena Milovanović, Milan Slavković, along with 12 additional attendees, including members of IMGGE’s Eco-Biotechnology Group

As part of the TwInn4MicroUp project’s capacity-building activities, a dedicated training session on the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Staff Exchange call was held at IMGGE on the 7th of December 2024. This training focused on fostering sustainable international and intersectoral cooperation through funded research staff exchanges between academic and non-academic sectors, including SMEs, across Europe and globally. The programme offered a detailed overview of the MSCA Staff Exchange mechanism, which supports mobility periods ranging from 1 to 12 months and promotes the development of collaborative R&I projects through personnel exchanges. Key

objectives include the acquisition of new skills, transfer of knowledge, and the strengthening of innovation capacities across sectors.

Lectures were delivered by Prof. Dr Goran Stojanović (EUTA) and Dr Ljiljana Mihajlović (Faculty of Chemistry), both of whom shared their practical experience in project development and implementation under Horizon Europe. In addition to practical proposal-writing advice, the training included a case study presentation of the MET-EFFECT project—an MSCA SE-funded initiative under Horizon Europe—offering participants a concrete example of successful project design and execution.

Figure 3. Material from the “MSCA Staff Exchange” training (IMGGE partner; Training No3).

4) Training title: **How to Write the IMPACT Section for a Horizon Europe Project**

Organiser: Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering (IMGGE), University of Belgrade

Date: 13th May 2025

Location: Belgrade, Serbia

Consortium Participant(s): Milan Slavković and Ivana Aleksić, along with 18 additional attendees

As part of the Twinn4MicroUp project’s strategic efforts to enhance proposal-writing competencies, a dedicated workshop titled How to Write the IMPACT Section for a Horizon Europe Project was held at IMGGE on the 13th of May 2025. The session was delivered by Ratko Bojovic and was designed to help participants effectively develop one of the most critical components of Horizon Europe proposals—the IMPACT section.

The training offered a comprehensive overview of how to define and articulate the potential scientific, societal, and economic impacts of a proposed project. Participants received expert guidance on identifying key stakeholders, understanding their needs, and mapping those needs to the project’s anticipated outcomes. Special emphasis was placed on how to clearly present these elements in line with the European Commission’s expectations.

Key topics included methods for conducting baseline and benchmark analyses, strategies for designing effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) plans, and techniques for structuring the IMPACT section. Participants learned how to clearly define target groups, align project results with identified needs, outline measurable outcomes, and describe long-term impacts. The training also addressed the identification of potential risks and barriers to impact, along with practical approaches for their mitigation.

Figure 4. Material from the “How to Write the IMPACT Section for a Horizon Europe Project” (IMGGE partner; Training No4).

3.1.2 TUS partner

1| Training Title: **TUS Industry Research & Funding Opportunities Workshop Event**

Organizer: TUS

Date: 28th March 2025

Location: Athlone, Ireland

Consortium Participant(s): Dr. Eduardo Lanzagorta, along with 30+ members of TUS Research staff.

As part of efforts to foster innovation and international collaboration, the Enterprise Ireland Research Funding Opportunities Workshop took place at the TUS Athlone Campus on Friday, 28th March. The event, organized in partnership with the Enterprise Europe Network and led by Enterprise Ireland's Research & Innovation team, brought together academic and industry participants to explore a range of funding and support instruments available for business growth and research development. The event included informative presentations, a Q&A session, and a networking lunch, creating a dynamic environment for exchanging ideas and building connections. The workshop was designed to help participants better understand how to access financial support for collaborative and innovative projects, with a special focus on expanding business ventures internationally. Led by experts such as Ann Dooley, Stephen O'Reilly, Dr. Sergio Ceballos Fernandez, Mark Sweeney, and Dr. Daniela Angione, the event offered valuable networking opportunities and direct access to national and European funding specialists. The interactive format encouraged open discussion and knowledge exchange, making it an ideal setting for anyone looking to advance their research, business ideas, or collaborative projects within a supportive and expert-led environment.

TUS INDUSTRY RESEARCH & FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES WORKSHOP EVENT

This workshop will offer academic and industry attendees an opportunity to hear about funding and supports available, to innovate, and to grow their business and collaborative ideas in a supported way through the Enterprise Ireland and Horizon Europe funding and support instruments

If you are interested in growing your business with an eye on **international collaboration** and **seeking funding to support** you to do so, then this is a worthwhile event for you.

- Friday 28th March TUS, Athlone Campus, 11 am – 1 pm, Main Building, Room B54
- Booking is advisable using the following link : [MS Forms](#)
- Tea/Coffee on arrival followed by presentations from the Enterprise Ireland Team, Q&A and a networking lunch.

Led by Enterprise Ireland Research & Innovation Presenters:

Ann Dooley
 Ann holds the position of Senior Technology Transfer Expert within the Enterprise Europe Network and also works as a Eureka Technical Expert. The Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) supports businesses and research organizations in their efforts to innovate and expand internationally by providing services that include collaborative partnership opportunities, licensing options, and distribution avenues.

Stephen O'Reilly
 Global Challenges & European Industrial Competitiveness
 National Contact Point

Dr Sergio Ceballos Fernandez
 Global Challenges & European Industrial Competitiveness
 National Contact Point

Mark Sweeney
 Global Challenges & European Industrial Competitiveness
 National Contact Point

Dr Daniela Angione
 Innovative Europe
 National Contact Point

In collaboration with TUS RISE

TUS RISE is co-funded by the Government of Ireland and the European Union through the ERDF Southern, Eastern & Midland Regional Programme 2021-27.

Figure 5. Event information poster from the “TUS Industry Research & Funding Opportunities” workshop (TUS Partner; Training No1).

2|Training Title: PathWays to Impact Roadshow

Organizer: TUS

Date: 30th May 2025

Location: Athlone, Ireland

Consortium Participant(s): TUS Research Staff and Students. Industrial partners and enterprises.

The TUS RISE Pathways to Impact Roadshow, was organized by the TUS Research, Development & Innovation office, and co-funded by the Government of Ireland and the European Union through

the ERDF Southern, Eastern & Midland Regional Programme 2021–27. This event was designed to bring together SMEs, industry partners, students, researchers, and enterprises from across the region, offering a dynamic platform for discovering research funding opportunities and fostering collaboration. Participants were welcomed with a keynote address from David Flood, Enterprise Ireland & COST National Coordinator, who provided an overview of accessible European funding programmes for academic staff and advanced PhD students.

Throughout the day, attendees engaged in insightful panel discussions featuring TUS researchers and regional enterprise leaders, who shared their experiences and best practices in securing funding and driving innovation. The event also offered dedicated sessions for industry challenges consultations and networking, allowing businesses to connect directly with TUS staff and researchers to discuss real-world issues and opportunities for partnership. Supported by the Faculty of Business & Hospitality, the Roadshow highlighted the importance of innovation and enterprise in the Midlands, providing valuable insights into the research funding process and encouraging new collaborations within the regional ecosystem.

Pathways to Impact Roadshow

TUS, Athlone Campus - Friday 30th May 9:30 to 14:00 - Douglas Hyde
Lecture Theatre

This complimentary event is designed for SMEs, industry collaborators, students, researchers, and enterprises. Join us to gain valuable insights into the research funding process, connect with experts and industry leaders from across the region, and explore opportunities for collaboration and innovation.

09:30	Tea/Coffee, Registration & Networking
09:50	Opening Address
10:00	Keynote Speaker - David Flood (Enterprise Ireland & COST National Coordinator) - Overview of COST, an accessible European funding programme for academic staff and advanced PhD students.
10:20	Panel: TUS Researchers & Regional Enterprises - Insights into the funding application process and its benefits from successful applicants. Dr. Romina Pezzoli - APT (Packaging Platform Lead), Dr. Charlene Connolly - Teagasc (Research and Innovation Programme Manager, Meat Technology Ireland), Naiara de Farias - Chemical Engineer, Arran Chemical Company Ltd. Dr. Mary McDonnell Naughton - Senior Lecturer / Chairperson, Research Ethics Committee, TUS, Dr. Mary Doolan - Integrated Care Programme for Older Persons (ICPOP), Operational Lead - Laois/Offaly
11:05	BREAK
11:20	Panel: The Future Works: Employment, Innovation & Enterprise in the Midlands: How the Faculty of Business & Hospitality Supports Regional SMEs <i>Supported by Faculty of Business & Hospitality</i>
12:05	Industry Challenges Consultations & Networking: A chance for businesses and enterprises to consult with TUS staff & researchers on their challenges. <i>Topics based on feedback submitted in advance via the registration form.</i>
13:00	Close & Lunch.

TUS RISE is co-funded by the Government of Ireland and the European Union through the ERDF Southern, Eastern & Midland Regional Programme 2021-27.

Figure 6. Event information and agenda poster from the “Pathways to Impact Roadshow” event (TUS Partner; Training No2).

3.1.3 UNIBA partner

1| Training Title: Info Day Horizon Europe - European Partnerships | Bando 2025 CBE JU (Call 2025 CBE JU)

Organiser: APRE (Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea)

Date: 16th April 2025

Location: Online

Consortium Participant(s): Prof. Gennaro Agrimi

On April 16, 2025, the Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (APRE), The Agency for the Promotion of European Research supports and facilitates Italian participation in the European Union's research and innovation (R&I) funding programs through information, training, and assistance services, in collaboration with the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) and the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), hosted the national information event titled “INFO DAY HORIZON EUROPE – EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIPS | 2025 CBE JU Call.” The event followed the European-level info day held on April 3, 2025, in Brussels.

Format and Participation: The event was conducted online from 10:00 AM to 1:00 PM CET, attracting a wide audience of stakeholders from academia, industry, and public institutions interested in bio-based innovation and European funding opportunities.

Purpose and Objectives: The primary goal of the Info Day was to present the 2025 CBE JU Call for Proposals, provide detailed insights into the CBE JU Annual Work Programme 2025, facilitate understanding of the 13 funding topics available under the call, and encourage and support Italian participation in the Horizon Europe framework.

The 2025 CBE JU Call features a total budget of €165 million, aimed at fostering the development of competitive circular bio-based industries across Europe. During the event, European and national experts delivered presentations that offered strategic guidance on proposal preparation, eligibility criteria, and evaluation processes. A central theme of the Info Day was the emphasis on public-private partnerships and cross-sector collaboration as essential drivers for achieving the European Union’s sustainability and circular economy objectives.

Participants gained valuable knowledge on how to engage with the CBE JU partnership and effectively leverage EU funding for research and innovation in the bioeconomy sector. APRE and its partners reaffirmed their commitment to supporting stakeholders through ongoing training, proposal review services, and opportunities for networking and collaboration.

The event has been recorded and can be found here: [\(1\) INFO DAY HORIZON EUROPE - EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIPS | Bando 2025 CBE JU - YouTube](#)

Figure 5. Material from the “Info Day Horizon Europe - European Partnerships” (UNIBA partner; Training No1).

2| Training Title: Innovation Management Laboratory

Organiser: UNIBA

Date: 16th April 2025

Location: online

Consortium Participant(s): Prof. Isabella Pisano, Giuseppe Martimucci (PhD student), Roberto Liberti (PhD student)

The Innovation Management Laboratory is a specialized academic course designed to provide doctoral candidates and medical residents with practical and theoretical tools in the field of innovation management. The course is led by Ilaria Re, Chief Operating Officer at the Italtotec Consortium and adjunct professor at both the University of Milan and the University of Bologna. Her dual role in academia and industry ensures a rich and applied learning experience for participants.

The course introduces participants to the core principles and methodologies of innovation management, guiding them from the ideation of new products and processes to the drafting of research proposals eligible for European and international funding. It also covers the operational aspects of managing funded research and development projects, offering a comprehensive view of the innovation lifecycle.

Structured over a total of 32 hours, the course is scheduled across eight sessions held between February and April. Sessions take place in the morning, from 9:00 AM to 1:00 PM, and are

organized into modules lasting either three or four hours. The academic value of the course is recognized with the allocation of four university credits (CFU). Assessment is based on a final evaluation of suitability, without a numerical grade.

The course is particularly relevant for early-stage researchers seeking to enhance their ability to conceptualize, plan, and manage innovation-driven projects. By combining academic rigor with practical application, it aims to empower participants to actively contribute to the development of competitive research proposals and to navigate the complexities of innovation funding landscapes.

UniBa UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO

COMPETENZE TRASVERSALI 2025

LABORATORIO DI INNOVATION MANAGEMENT

PROPOSAL WRITING DI PROGETTI DI RICERCA E SVILUPPO

Il corso introduce i principi e i metodi di gestione dell'innovazione, dall'ideazione di nuovi prodotti e processi, alla stesura di progetti di ricerca finanziati da fondi europei e di cooperazione internazionale fino alla gestione operativa.

- 1** CHE COS'È L'INNOVATION MANAGEMENT?
- 2** COME ACCEDERE AI FONDI EUROPEI PER LA RICERCA E SVILUPPO INDUSTRIALE.
- 3** DALL'IDEA AL PROGETTO.

ORGANIZZAZIONE
 Durata: 32 ore.
 CFU: 4.
 Moduli da 3 - 4 ore nella fascia oraria 9:00-13:00.
 Le lezioni saranno svolte su piattaforma Microsoft Teams.

CALENDARIO
 Febbraio: 18, 25.
 Marzo: 4, 11, 18, 25.
 Aprile: 1, 8.

ILARIA RE
 Chief Operating Officer presso il Consorzio Italbiotec e Professore a contratto di Gestione dell'Innovazione presso l'Università degli Studi di Milano e presso l'Università di Bologna

ISCRIVITI QUI

Figure 6. Material from the “Innovation Management Laboratory” (UNIBA partner; Training No2).

3| Training Title: TarCirTech Initiative

Organiser: Tondo – Circular Economy (non-profit organization)

Date: 16th May 2025

Location: Taranto (Apulia, Italy)

Consortium Participant(s): 4 PhD students (Giuseppe Martimucci, Roberto Liberti, Silvia D'Eusebio and Loris Savino) and 1 tenure-track researcher (Nicola Di Fidio)

The Taranto CirTech initiative stands as a pioneering model for regional innovation, designed to position the city of Taranto as a national and international reference point for circular economy solutions. Developed by Tondo, a non-profit organization committed to promoting regenerative and circular models and supported by the MUSA project under Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), the initiative integrates research, entrepreneurship, and advanced technologies to address some of the most pressing environmental and socio-economic challenges of our time.

At the heart of Taranto CirTech is a structured innovation pathway that mirrors the lifecycle of a successful research proposal. The program includes a Hackathon, a Call4Ideas, an acceleration program, and a matchmaking phase—each designed to guide participants from the early stages of problem identification and ideation through to project development, stakeholder engagement, and implementation planning. This structure not only fosters innovation but also cultivates the essential skills needed to write and manage competitive research proposals.

The initiative's thematic focus on sectors such as the blue economy, agri-food systems, renewable energy, waste and water management, and sustainable materials aligns closely with the strategic priorities of major European funding programs, including Horizon Europe, LIFE, and Interreg. Moreover, its emphasis on deep tech—including artificial intelligence, biotechnology, blockchain, and advanced materials—equips participants to respond effectively to calls that demand interdisciplinary, high-impact solutions.

A compelling example of the initiative's impact is the success of the Micro4Biotech team, which won the Taranto CirTech Hackathon with their project SHELLULOSE. Comprising four PhD students and one early-career researcher, the team proposed an innovative process to convert mussel shells and waste whey—two underutilized by-products—into high-value biotechnological products through chemical and biochemical valorisation. Their project exemplifies how applied research can be transformed into a scalable, sustainable solution with real-world impact.

SHELLULOSE not only addresses environmental sustainability by reducing waste but also demonstrates the potential for circular bioeconomy models to generate economic value. The project's scientific rigor, originality, and alignment with EU sustainability goals make it a strong candidate for future funding under European research and innovation programs.

The hackathon itself served as a dynamic platform for collaboration, creativity, and knowledge exchange. It provided participants with the opportunity to refine their ideas, receive expert feedback, and practice articulating their solutions in a format that closely resembles the structure of a research proposal. This hands-on experience is invaluable for early-stage researchers and innovators seeking to secure funding and bring their ideas to life.

In conclusion, Taranto CirTech is more than an innovation accelerator—it is a practical training ground for developing the skills and strategies necessary to write successful, fundable research proposals. By bridging the gap between academic research and entrepreneurial application, the initiative empowers participants to transform innovative ideas into impactful projects that contribute to the circular transition and sustainable development at both local and European levels.

Figure 7. Material from the “TarCirTech Initiative” (UNIBA partner; Training No3).

3.1.4 NTUA partner

1| Training Title: **Proposal Writing**

Organizer(s): EXELISIS¹ and AXIA INNOVATION²

Date: 6th – 7th May 2025

Location: online

Consortium Participant(s): Christina Ferousi

EXELISIS is an engineering-based consulting company in Athens, Greece, offering customized business development and innovation services, particularly in materials and energy. With over 15 years of international experience, its team of engineers, economists, and analysts supports clients

¹ <https://www.exelisis.gr/>

² <https://www.axia-innovation.com/en/home/>

through tailored strategies in project management, innovation, and communication. EXELISIS also specializes in research services, engineering studies, and dissemination activities within European research projects.

The two-day Proposal Writing Seminar provided participants with both theoretical and practical insights into crafting successful Horizon Europe proposals. *Day 1* began with an introduction to the seminar’s objectives, followed by a comprehensive overview of the Horizon Europe program, including its goals, structure, funding schemes, and eligibility requirements. Sessions covered in-depth topic analysis, concept development, and strategies for identifying project gaps, partners, and drafting concept notes. The seminar then explored the three main sections of a Horizon Europe proposal: Excellence (objectives, methodology, interdisciplinary approach, TRL, gender dimensions, Open Science), Impact (expected outcomes, wider impact, dissemination, exploitation, business plan, IPR), and Implementation (work packages, risk management, cost justification, consortium structure). The day concluded with a session analysing lessons from past successful and unsuccessful proposals from an evaluator’s perspective. *Day 2* was hands-on, beginning with group exercises on reading and analysing call topics using AI tools, followed by practical work on structuring proposals. The afternoon sessions addressed best practices, common pitfalls, and how to effectively write each section of a proposal. The seminar wrapped up with a recap, Q&A, and a discussion of the next steps and follow-up actions.

Figure 8. Material from the “Proposal Writing” (NTUA partner; Training No1).

3.2 Planned Trainings

1| Training Title: **Effective Project Planning and Execution**

Organizer(s): TwInn4MicroUp

Date: 7th July 2025

Place: online

As part of the TwInn4MicroUp project's capacity-building and training activities, a seminar titled "Effective Project Planning and Execution" is scheduled to take place online via Microsoft Teams on the 7th of July 2025. This half-day event (12:00–16:45 CET) aims to strengthen the participants' competencies in designing and planning competitive research projects, with a particular focus on the pre-award phase. The agenda includes targeted sessions on building a successful consortium, stakeholder analysis, structuring work packages, budget planning, and designing pathways to impact. Emphasis will also be placed on practical tools such as Gantt charts and risk management tables. The seminar is structured to combine expert-led presentations with interactive elements, including an Experience Sharing Session featuring invited speakers with significant experience in research funding and project management. Contributions will include insights from Máire Brophy (TUS), Dr. Kieran Dowd (TUS), Dr. Noel Gately (APT Technology Gateway), and Dr. N. Fokialakis (University of Athens), who will reflect on real-world challenges and best practices. The event will conclude with an open discussion session led by the Research Support Team of the Technological University of the Shannon, encouraging active engagement and knowledge exchange among participants.

Effective Project Planning and Execution Seminar

7th July 2025, 12:00 -16:45 CET, via Microsoft Teams

Máire Brophy, PhD
20+ years of expertise in research funding and strategy, with a strong track record in leading and supporting successful national and European proposals; a recognized trainer in research development, with a focus on interdisciplinary excellence

Dr Kieran Dowd, Lecturer
Co-ordinator of the INDEEP (INvention on the DEterminants of, and Expertise in, Physical activity behaviours) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Network that provides innovative and interdisciplinary research and training in physical activity and health promotion

Dr Noel Gately, Centre Manager
Expert in knowledge transfer and industry-academia collaboration, with a background in managing applied research centres; former Centre Manager at the APT Technology Gateway, supporting innovation in polymer technologies through national and EU co-funded initiatives

Dr N. Fokialakis, Associate Professor
20+ years of expertise in applying, negotiating and implementing projects funded under FP7, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe in the research field of natural products and their applications as innovative cosmetics, food supplements and pharmaceutical products.

Take a look at the detailed agenda on the next page

[Register here](#)

Effective Project Planning and Execution Seminar Agenda

12.00–12.10 Introductions

12.10–12.30 Coordinator and Project Manager: roles, approaches, activities and expertise

12.30–12.45 Managing your consortium

12.45–13.15 Different types of projects and consortia

13.15–13.30 **Break**

13.30–14.00 **Building your consortium**

- Qualities of a good consortium
- How to identify and find partners

Stakeholder analysis exercise

14.00–14.15 **Building and managing your budget**

14.15–14.40 **Implementing your project: examples of organisational structures, Gantt charts and risk tables**

14.40–15.00 **Delivering your project: deliverables, milestones and pathways to impact**

15.00–15.30 **Break**

Experience Sharing Session

15.30–15.45 **Dr Kieran Dowd, Lecturer**
Faculty of Science and Health, Department of Sport and Health Science, Technological University of the Shannon, Ireland

15.45–16.00 **Dr Noel Gately, Centre Manager**
Applied Polymer Technologies Gateway, Technological University of the Shannon, Ireland

16.00–16.15 **Dr N. Fokialakis, Associate Professor**
Section of Pharmacognosy and Natural Product Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Athens, Greece

16.15–16.45 **Open Questions Session**
Michelle Cooney & Lorna Walsh, Research Support team, Technological University of the Shannon, Ireland

Figure 9. Agenda flyer of the upcoming “Effective Project Planning and Execution” seminar.

2) Training Title: Advanced Administrative Skills for Project Managers

Organizer(s): TwInn4MicroUp

Date: 24th July 2025

Place: online

As part of the TwInn4MicroUp project’s post-award capacity-building efforts, a one-day training session titled "EU Horizon Europe Project Implementation – NuaFund Training Session" is scheduled for the 24th of July 2025. Delivered in collaboration with NuaFund and hosted online, the session is designed to enhance participants’ practical knowledge of implementing Horizon Europe projects. The morning session (10:00–12:00 CET) will focus on the essentials of project set-up and governance, including institutional responsibilities and coordination structures, followed by a dedicated segment on financial management in Horizon Europe and an open Q&A. The afternoon session (13:00–15:00 CET) will dive into key post-award topics such as the EU Funding & Tenders Portal, communication and exploitation strategies (with a focus on impact),

open science practices, data management and ethics, and intellectual property (IP) management. The session will conclude with a forward-looking discussion on the roadmap to Framework Programme 10 (FP10).

3) Training Title: **Proposal Writing and Funds Acquisition Seminar**

Organizer(s): TwInn4MicroUp consortium; adjacent to the Joint Conference of the MikroBioKosmos Society & The Central and East Europe Symposium of Microbial Ecology³

Date: 22nd September 2025

Place: Thessaloniki, Greece

This satellite seminar is organized within the framework of the biannual Mikrobiokosmos International Conference, under the auspices of the Hellenic Scientific Society of Mikrobiokosmos and in collaboration with the International Society for Microbial Ecology (ISME). Mikrobiokosmos, founded in 2007, serves as Greece's national platform for advancing research and innovation in microbial ecology, environmental microbiology, microbial biotechnology, and related fields. With over 150 academic, research, and industrial members from Greece and Cyprus, the society fosters scientific exchange and international collaboration, particularly across the Balkans and Eastern Mediterranean. ISME, a global leader in microbial ecology, supports research dissemination, networking, and training through symposia, publications, and grant programs. Through expert perspectives and interactive dialogue, the "Proposal Writing and Funds Acquisition Seminar" aims to empower early-career researchers with the tools and strategies to advance their professional trajectories. It will offer critical insights into research funding opportunities and academic career pathways, featuring invited talks from:

 Kyriaki Kalaitzidou⁴, Associate Chair for Faculty Development, Rae S. and Frank H. Neely Professor, George W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA

 Mary Allen⁵, Professor of Biology, Hartwick College, USA

³ <https://afea.eventsair.com/mbkceesme2025/>

⁴ <https://www.me.gatech.edu/faculty/kalaitzidou>

⁵ <https://www.hartwick.edu/people/mary-allen/>

- **Eleni Zika**⁶, Head of Sector for Scientific Impact and Feedback to Policy, European Research Council
- **Michael Sauer**⁷, Head of Department of Biotechnology, OMV, Austria
- **Kalliopi Chalkou**⁸, Head of Quality, Safety and Environment Governance, Coca-Cola HBC

4. Submitted Proposals

4.1 IMGGE partner

IMGGE Proposal #1	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN (EIC Pathfinder 2025)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101258471
Title	Sustainable, high-performing aerogels for biopreservation and bioremediation
Acronym	PHAbble
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	~ 2.9 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	21 May 2025
Abstract	PHAbble focus on sustainable production of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), green downstream processing, and advanced materials' engineering to develop high-performance and eco-friendly aerogels for practical applications in biological preservation and environmental remediation. PHAbble uses RUCO (recovered used cooking oil) and their derivatives as feedstocks for the biosynthesis of tailored PHAs'

⁶ <https://erc.europa.eu/event-speaker/elena-zika>

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/michael-sauer-wien/?originalSubdomain=at>

⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/kalliopi-chalkou-46a82122/?originalSubdomain=gr>

IMGGE Proposal #1	
	<p>composition, creating a closed-loop value chain that reduces waste, fossil plastic reliance, carbon emissions, and environmental impact, aligning with EU sustainability goals. PHAbble’s novel aerogels are based on PHAs, bio-based, biodegradable and biocompatible polyesters that will be combined with specific natural compounds or enzymes, delivering effective functional materials for (1) Preservation of biological materials: functional PHA aerogels provide microenvironments that protect cellular integrity that can revolutionize cell storage, reduce dependence on toxic cryoprotectants, and enhance sensitive cell recovery for medical applications, and (2) Bioremediation: catalytic PHA aerogels carrying specialized enzymes will capture and remove microplastics and oil pollutants from ecosystems, offering a biodegradable and bioreactive solution to pollution. Through green chemistry approaches and sustainable engineering, PHAbble aims to establish PHA aerogels as a groundbreaking platform for high-performance, eco-friendly applications in biological storage and environmental restoration.</p>
Result	Pending

IMGGE Proposal #2	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01 (EIC Pathfinder Challenges 2024)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101223167
Title	NATURAL FIBER-BASED BIOPOLYMER COMPOSITES FOR FOOD PACKAGING AND AGRICULTURE
Acronym	FIBPAK
Type*	HORIZON Lump Sum Grant

IMGGE Proposal #2	
Budget	~ 4 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	15 October 2024
Abstract	<p>The FIBPAK project aims to develop sustainable, fiber-reinforced biocomposites for food packaging and agricultural applications, offering an eco-friendly alternative to fossil-based plastics. By utilizing natural fibers sourced from renewable resources such as wood, algae, and bacteria, FIBPAK addresses key environmental challenges while promoting a circular economy model. The project integrates advanced material science, biotechnology, and innovative processing technologies to produce biodegradable and recyclable packaging solutions with high fiber content, reducing the environmental footprint of plastic waste. Key objectives of the project include developing sustainable natural fiber feedstocks, improving fiber-polymer compatibility, innovating bio-based additives, and creating scalable prototypes for industrial applications. The project will also focus on ensuring the recyclability and biodegradability of its products, contributing to European sustainability goals and regulations such as the EU Circular Economy Action Plan and the Plastics Strategy.</p> <p>The consortium behind FIBPAK is multidisciplinary, bringing together experts in material science, processing technology, and recycling from various organizations across Europe. The project is structured into several work packages, addressing fiber extraction, modification, biocomposite development, and end-of-life recycling. To ensure effective management and oversight, FIBPAK has established key governing bodies, including the Advisory Board (AB), Project Steering Committee (PSC), Ethical Council (ETC), and Technical Coordination Team (TCT). These teams will ensure that the project aligns with ethical standards, gender diversity, and technical goals while fostering collaboration across disciplines. Ultimately,</p>

IMGGE Proposal #2	
	FIBPAK aims to contribute to the broader adoption of fiber-based materials across industries, moving toward a more sustainable, circular economy.
Result	Not funded (<i>10.5 out of 15</i>)

IMGGE Proposal #3	
Call	IDEAS 2024
Topic	/
Type of Action	National call
Proposal	
No	/
Title	Bio-based solutions for the next generation sustainable materials, advanced recycling and future material design
Acronym	BioSMARTICS
Budget	299000
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	25/02/2025
Abstract	<p>The BioSMARTICS project will develop next generation smart biomaterials powered by microorganisms, to address critical global challenges like resource depletion, pollution, and waste accumulation. With each person in Europe generating over 180 kg of packaging waste and nearly 300 kg of food waste annually, there is an urgent need for sustainable solutions. As global demand for such solutions rises, BioSMARTICS project aims to transform various industries by widening application of advanced bio-based materials while simultaneously reducing plastic, paper, and food waste, thereby supporting a circular economy. The project harnesses the powers of biotechnology and synthetic biology to design and create biomaterials with customized functions. By leveraging the efficient biosynthetic processes of microorganisms, BioSMARTICS will develop hybrid biomaterials with unique properties such as self-organization,</p>

IMGGE Proposal #3

	<p>adaptive environmental responses and full biodegradation. These advanced biomaterials hold promise for applications in green packaging, bioremediation, sensing technologies, and wider. BioSMARTICS focuses on utilizing bacterial biopolymers like polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), nanocellulose (BNC), and bio-based poly(lactic acid) (PLA), combining them with advanced biological additives (pigments, magnetosomes, enzymes and bacterial spores) to enhance material properties and functionality while maintaining safety. The project addresses key biomanufacturing challenges, including scaling processes, improving biomaterial properties, and ensuring sustainable end-of-life solutions. It will also engage young designers and artists to foster social acceptance and promote next generation bio-based products. With a team of 15 researchers from fields including microbiology, molecular biology, material science, design and conservation, the project brings together complementary skills and knowledge from two leading institutions: The Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering and the Faculty of Applied Arts at the University Belgrade. In addition, international experts from the PRISM Manufacturing Research Institute in Ireland and the National Technical University of Athens will contribute expertise in material processing, biotechnology, and industrial applications. Ultimately, BioSMARTICS' eco-innovative solutions have the potential to improve industries, significantly reduce global environmental impacts, and shape the future of sustainable manufacturing.</p>
Result	Pending

4.2 TUS partner

TUS Proposal #1	
Call	Interreg North-West Europe 2021 - 2027
Topic	Promoting the transition to a circular and resource-efficient economy
Type of Action	NWE Joint Strategies and Action Plans
Proposal	
No	NWE0500911
Title	Green Textile Recycling: Zero-Waste-Cycle
Acronym	G-TEX-0
Type*	Transnational cooperation grant funded under the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).
Budget	~ 1.9 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	15 January 2025
Abstract	<p>NWE faces significant challenges in achieving a circular textile economy, including excessive amounts of non-recyclable textile waste and inefficient resource use, which result in substantial environmental damage and economic losses. The overall objective of G-TEX-0 is to drive a more effective and balanced transition toward a circular textile economy in NWE. The project aims to reduce textile waste, minimize environmental impacts, and optimize resource use by developing industry-compatible, cost-effective green re- and upcycling methods. Expected changes include increased recycling rates and the creation of sustainable value chains that align with the waste hierarchy principles: reduce, reuse, and re- and up-cycle. The project will deliver three key outputs: (i) An extruder-based green recycling technology for breaking down the polyester segment of textile waste into monomers, as well as developing a feasible separation method for the polyester/cotton blends waste, (ii) the reuse of polyester fibers through a decolorization process, which enables continuous fiber to-fiber re-and upcycling, (iii) biopolymer production from recycled</p>

TUS Proposal #1	
	<p>materials. These solutions will critically reduce dependence on fossil oil-based raw materials, replace harmful synthetic chemicals, and lower greenhouse gas emissions associated with fiber and raw material production. G-TEX-0 combines multiple innovations into a cohesive framework that provides comprehensive solutions for recycling colored polyester/cotton textiles, which are currently not feasible with existing methods, by developing industrial-scale protocols. These advancements will establish a benchmark for sustainable transformation textile industry by assisting SMEs with game-changing technologies, promoting awareness of society through an effective communication strategy, supporting policymakers in advancing regional sustainability goals, benefiting communities by reducing environmental harm, and promoting circular practices.</p>
Result	Not Funded (<i>Rejected at Stage 1</i>)

TUS Proposal #2	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN (EIC Pathfinder 2025)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101257388
Title	SUSTAINABLE AND HIGH-PERFORMANCE PACKAGING FROM SEAWEED AND USED COOKING OILS
Acronym	SUSHI-PACK
Type*	HORIZON-AG
Budget	~ 3 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	21 May 2025

TUS Proposal #2	
Abstract	<p>The packaging market highly relies on fossil-based plastics, which derive from non-renewable resources and producing products that are not biodegradable in different environments, increasing waste production. Renewable bio-based raw materials can be the alternative to produce safe and sustainable packaging materials. SUSHI-PACK will use sustainably sourced seaweed polysaccharides, especially alginate and agar, together with the secondary raw material Regenerated Used Cooking Oils.</p> <p>SUSHI-PACK will use advanced technologies in Metabolic Engineering and Biocatalysis to improve the production of hydroxy fatty acids from RUCO and for the production of a sustainable Bioprocess which can be further scaled-up at industrial scale. The SUSHI-PACK process is based on the use of biocatalytically produced hydroxy fatty acids and on their chemical transformation into polyesters, poly(ester urethane)s and modified polysaccharides, which will be processed in blends and multi-layer material to be tested in the packaging sector. Chemicals, polymers, additives and technologies will be chosen in terms of different Regulations and will be assayed with the SSbD framework to produce a process which can be fully sustainable both at the environmental, socio and economic scale. The latter, together with LCA, will aid to identify bottlenecks and to identify other chemicals or processes to improve their sustainability. The End of Life of the products will be assessed for different destinies: Compostability, Biodegradation and Enzymatic hydrolysis. Enzymatically hydrolyzed polymers and materials will also be tested for their revalorization as feedstock for the production of industrially valuable polymers, such as polyhydroxyalkanoates. SUSHI-PACK will offer sustainably and economically alternatives to fossil-based plastics, with a reduction of at least 15% of GHG emission and an economic turnover of 58 M€.</p>
Result	Pending

4.3 UNIBA partner

UNIBA Proposal #1	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDERCHALLENGE
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDERCHALLENGE
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC
Proposal	
No	101223138
Title	SUSTAINABLE AND HIGH-PERFORMANCE PACKAGING FROM SEAWEED AND USED COOKING OILS
Acronym	SUSHI-PACK
Type*	HORIZON Lump Sum Grant
Budget	~ 3.99 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	16/10/2024
Abstract	<p>The food packaging market highly relies on fossil-based plastics, which derive from non-renewable resources and producing products that are not biodegradable in different environments, increasing waste production.</p> <p>Renewable bio-based raw materials can be the alternative to produce safe and sustainable food packaging materials. SUSHI-PACK will use sustainably sourced seaweed polysaccharides, especially alginate and agar, together with the secondary raw material Regenerated Used Cooking Oils. SUSHI-PACK will use advanced technologies in Metabolic Engineering and Biocatalysis to improve the production of hydroxy fatty acids from RUCO and for the production of a sustainable Bioprocess which can be further scaled-up at industrial scale. The SUSHI-PACK process is based on the use of biocatalytically produced hydroxy fatty acids and on their chemical transformation into polyesters, poly(ester urethane)s and modified polysaccharides, which will be processed in blends and multi-layer material to be tested in the food packaging sector. Chemicals, polymers, additives and technologies will be chosen in terms of different</p>

UNIBA Proposal #1	
	Regulations especially for products in contact with food and will be assayed with the SSbD framework to produce a process which can be fully sustainable both at the environmental, socio and economic scale. The latter, together with LCA, will aid to identify bottlenecks and to identify other chemicals or processes to improve their sustainability. The End of Life of the products will be assessed for different destinies: Compostability, Biodegradation and Enzymatic hydrolysis. Enzymatically hydrolysed polymers and materials will also be tested for their revalorisation as feedstock for the production of industrially valuable polymers, such as polyhydroxyalkanoates. SUSHI-PACK will offer sustainably and economically alternatives to fossil-based plastics, with a reduction of at least 15% of GHG emission and an economic turnover of 22 M€.
Result	Not funded (<i>14.5 out of 15</i>)

UNIBA Proposal #2	
Call	ERASMUS-EDU-2025-PEX-EMJM-MOB
Topic	ERASMUS-EDU-2025-PEX-EMJM-MOB
Type of Action	ERASMUS-EMJM-UN
<i>Proposal</i>	
No	101241139
Title	Biorefinery European Master
Acronym	BIOREF
Type*	RASMUS-AG-UN
Budget	~ 2.1 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	16/10/2024
Abstract	The Master's course in Biorefinery (Bioref Master) is a two-year (120 ECTS) programme, entirely taught in English and jointly operated by four universities, (the Bioref Consortium): the University of Lille, France,

UNIBA Proposal #2	
	<p>Cracow University of Technology, Poland, the University Rey Juan Carlos, Spain, and University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy. Eligible students must hold a BSc in Chemistry, Chemical engineering, Physical Chemistry, Biochemistry or equivalent; have a high academic level and good command of the English language. The Bioref programme includes mandatory mobility of students within the Bioref Consortium, based on their choice of specialization according to our partners' expertise, and it leads for the time being to the award of multiple degree diplomas with a joint diploma supplement with the ultimate aim of producing a joint degree. The Bioref Joint Master's course focuses on biomass farming, harvesting and transformation process to high added value molecules. The Master course will provide the highest level of knowledge in these fields but also to bioeconomy and environmental changes occurring during biorefinery implementation. It will allow the students to enter directly to the labour market or follow a career in the research domain starting by a PhD.</p> <p>The Bioref Master's course provides all students with various transversal skills (competencies in entrepreneurship, project management, bibliographical search and synthesis in link with industry and knowledge of REACH legislation, LCA and TCA calculation and intellectual property issues). Additionally, during the 2 years of the programme (integration week, 4th semester research project, lab courses, theoretical course units) they will have opportunities to acquire other soft skills (intercultural communication, research experience and scientific communication, national language of their host universities) enabling them to easily adapt to their future international professional environment and an economic turnover of 22 M€.</p>
Result	Pending

UNIBA Proposal #3	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC
Proposal	
No	101223138
Title	SUSTAINABLE AND HIGH-PERFORMANCE PACKAGING FROM SEAWEED AND USED COOKING OILS
Acronym	SUSHI-PACK
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	~ 2.99 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	20/05/2025
Abstract	<p>The packaging market highly relies on fossil-based plastics, which derive from non-renewable resources and producing products that are not biodegradable in different environments, increasing waste production. Renewable bio-based raw materials can be the alternative to produce safe and sustainable packaging materials. SUSHI-PACK will use sustainably sourced seaweed polysaccharides, especially alginate and agar, together with the secondary raw material Regenerated Used Cooking Oils.</p> <p>SUSHI-PACK will use advanced technologies in Metabolic Engineering and Biocatalysis to improve the production of hydroxy fatty acids from RUCO and for the production of a sustainable Bioprocess which can be further scaled-up at industrial scale. The SUSHI-PACK process is based on the use of biocatalytically produced hydroxy fatty acids and on their chemical transformation into polyesters, poly(ester urethane)s and modified polysaccharides, which will be processed in blends and multi-layer material to be tested in the packaging sector. Chemicals, polymers, additives and technologies will be chosen in terms of different Regulations and will be assayed with the SSbD framework to produce a process which</p>

UNIBA Proposal #3	
	<p>can be fully sustainable both at the environmental, socio and economic scale. The latter, together with LCA, will aid to identify bottlenecks and to identify other chemicals or processes to improve their sustainability. The End of Life of the products will be assessed for different destinies: Compostability, Biodegradation and Enzymatic hydrolysis. Enzymatically hydrolysed polymers and materials will also be tested for their revalorization as feedstock for the production of industrially valuable polymers, such as polyhydroxyalkanoates. SUSHI-PACK will offer sustainably and economically alternatives to fossil-based plastics, with a reduction of at least 15% of GHG emission and an economic turnover of 58 M€.</p>
Result	Pending

4.4 NTUA partner

NTUA Proposal #1	
Call	HORIZON-JU-CBE-2024 (Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking)
Topic	HORIZON-JU-CBE-2024-RIA-05
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA (HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions)
<i>Proposal</i>	
No	101213568
Title	Advancing functional food components R and D: novel bioactive compounds from algae
Acronym	AFFOORDbio
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	~ 3.5 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	18 September 2024
Abstract	AFFOORDbio aims to revolutionize the European bioeconomy by advancing research on functional bio-based food and feed ingredients

NTUA Proposal #1	
	<p>sourced from underutilized algae. With a focus on sustainability, the project will harness innovative biotechnology and precision fermentation processes to transform currently unexploited algae into high-value bioactive compounds. These include antioxidants, prebiotics, and bioactive proteins, which can be integrated into both human food and animal feed systems. By maximizing algae's potential, the project seeks to address critical EU priorities such as food security, sustainability, and circular bioeconomy goals. The project's methodology includes the development of tools and systems for nutritional, environmental, and safety assessments, supported by a cutting-edge Digital Twin (DT) platform. This platform will enable real-time monitoring and provide stakeholders with detailed insights into production efficiency, environmental impacts, and scalability. AFFOORDbio's interdisciplinary approach emphasizes innovation, consumer awareness, and collaboration with industry stakeholders to ensure market readiness. The project's outcomes will contribute significantly to European Green Deal objectives by promoting sustainable food systems, reducing environmental footprints, and fostering bio-based economic growth across Europe.</p>
Result	Not Funded (<i>11 out of 15</i>)

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

NTUA Proposal #2	
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-ACCESS-01 (Teaming for Excellence)
Topic	HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-ACCESS-01-01-two-stage
Type of Action	HORIZON-CSA (HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions)
<i>Proposal</i>	
No	101250294-1
Title	Establishment of an AI Facilitated Circular Bioeconomy Centre of Excellence in Athens

NTUA Proposal #2	
Acronym	FABLE
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	15 m EUR
Duration	72 months
Submission Date	9 April 2025
Abstract	<p>Circular Bioeconomy and AI are fields of research that have the potential to improve the output of Academic and Industrial stakeholders in Greece. The establishment of a Circular Bioeconomy Centre of Excellence (CoE) supported by ethical use of AI in Athens will constitute a paradigm change for R&I and will catalyze structural changes in the Greek economy. The CoE will be hosted by the Agricultural University of Athens with the participation of the National and Kapodistrian University, and the National Technical University of Athens. Stakeholders from the public, agricultural and industrial sector will contribute to the establishment of the center and will benefit from its activities. The Technion – Israel Institute of Technology will support Greek initiatives in research, innovation, capacity building, and digital education. The Israeli Start-Up Nation Success Institute will play a strategic role in the consortium by driving entrepreneurship, innovation acceleration, and commercialization in Greece’s emerging bioeconomy. The consortium has the required critical mass of expertise and involves all the necessary sectors for implementing a significant paradigm shift in the Greek circular bioeconomy ecosystem. Thus, policy changes that support collaboration of the academic, industrial and public sector will be introduced and will ensure the sustainable operation of the CoE after the end of the project. Representative lines of research envisioned are AI facilitated biomass exploitation for chemicals production, biorefineries and biosensors based on nanotechnology. The CoE will be hosted within a legal framework ensuring full administrative and financial independence under Greek law. Thus, the CoE will operate</p>

NTUA Proposal #2	
	with its decision-making authority in legal, staffing, financial, and academic matters. This structure ensures compliance with Horizon Europe expectations and will reinforce the CoE's role as a leader in bioeconomy innovation and R&I reform in Greece. Material development data will be shared with an AI tool, developed by a sister project, to expand the data pool and refine material development and biodegradability predictions. This project will support the European Circular Economy Action Plan by fostering scalable, sustainable solutions that reduce waste and plastic pollution while promoting resource efficiency.
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

NTUA Proposal #3	
Call	Section 1 – Food Value-chain in the Nexus 2024 <i>Program:</i> PRIMA – Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (2018 – 2028)
Topic	1.3.1 (IA) Developing cost-effective and sustainable technologies adapted to Mediterranean Food Systems to decrease food loss and waste
Type of Action	Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA) / Innovation Action (IA)
<i>Proposal</i>	
No	N/A
Title	Regenerative upcycling Food and Packaging technologies for boosting Mediterranean food system circularity and sustainability
Acronym	REGENERATION4FOOD
Type*	70% funding rate with exceptions
Budget	~4.6 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	9 April 2024 (<i>stage 1</i>) / 25 September 2024 (<i>stage 2</i>)

NTUA Proposal #3	
Abstract	<p>This project aims to develop sustainable, knowledge-driven solutions tailored to Mediterranean food systems to reduce food loss and waste (FLW) while promoting a dietary shift toward high-quality plant-based foods. It addresses key challenges in product safety, nutritional value, and consumer acceptance by advancing innovations in green post-harvest processing, clean-label food strategies, and bio-based packaging. A strong focus is placed on microbiome-enabled fermentation to enhance the sensory, nutritional, and functional properties of plant foods and to valorise FLW. The project will deliver two repurposed plant-based snacks and two beverages, industrial-scale bio-packaging, and green bioprocessing protocols. Three novel microbial starter cultures will be developed and commercialized, supporting both food production and packaging innovation. Expected outcomes include the market introduction of four bio-designed plant products, patented sustainable bioprocessing technologies, and integration of safety data into policy frameworks. Scientific outputs will be widely disseminated, with high expected citation impact. The project will drive significant economic, environmental, and societal benefits: reducing food prices and FLW, boosting plant food consumption, enabling 65,000 new green jobs, and contributing to improved health outcomes and biodiversity preservation. Through training of 12 early-career researchers and targeted stakeholder engagement, the project will catalyse broad adoption across the Mediterranean region.</p>
Result	Not Funded (<i>15.17 out of 17.5</i>)

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

NTUA Proposal #4	
Call	European Regional Development Fund of the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness,

NTUA Proposal #4	
	Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH-INNOVATE (2021-2027)
Topic	<u>Priority Area of the ESIF 2021-2027</u> : Agri-food Chain <u>Subcategory</u> : 03.06.03 High Nutritional Value Products & Sustainability of the Natural Environment
Type of Action	Intervention II: Partnerships between Businesses and Research Organizations
Proposal	
No	EKΠΑΡ02-0082369
Title	Production and exploitation of fungal protein from edible mushrooms for the development of innovative food products
Acronym	MushEat
Type*	Grant Budget-Based; 100%
Budget	~1.5 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	13 September 2024
Abstract	The MushEat project unites two Greek companies (Dirfis and Kentris) with two academic institutions (AUA and NTUA) to develop sustainable, high-nutritional-value food products based on mushrooms, their mycelium, bioactive extracts, and enzymatic preparations. Edible Basidiomycetes from Greek habitats will be screened for their ability to produce protein-rich biomass and valuable enzymes using agro-industrial residues as substrates. Selected strains will be cultivated through optimized biotechnological processes at laboratory, pilot, and commercial scale. The project also explores heterologous expression of fungal enzymes for food applications. The resulting biomass and bioactives will be incorporated into innovative food prototypes, whose stability, sensory properties, and environmental footprint will be thoroughly assessed. MushEat aims to

NTUA Proposal #4	
	create at least three novel food products aligned with circular economy principles, offering both nutritional benefits and market potential.
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

NTUA Proposal #5	
Call	European Regional Development Fund of the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH-INNOVATE (2021-2027)
Topic	Priority Area of the ESIF 2021-2027: Environment – Circular Economy Subcategory: 04.08.02 Utilization of residues from secondary raw material production for the manufacturing of high added-value products
Type of Action	Intervention II: Partnerships between Businesses and Research Organizations
Proposal	
No	EKIIAP02-0062853
Title	A Novel and Efficient Biorefinery Utilizing Low-cost Resources for Producing Advanced Biofuels and Biochemicals via Industrial Symbiosis
Acronym	NEBULA
Type*	Grant Budget-Based; 100%
Budget	~1.5 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission date	13 September 2024
Abstract	The NEBULA project aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative industrial symbiosis model based on sustainable microbial bioconversion technologies. It involves three companies operating in distinct sectors: a biofuels producer, a dairy producer with an anaerobic digestion unit, and a manufacturer of soil conditioners. The model promotes the direct exchange

NTUA Proposal #5	
	and valorisation of gaseous, liquid, and solid waste streams between the companies as feedstocks for microbial biomass production. This biomass provides valuable biochemicals that enhance raw materials and products across the value chain. The project's core objective is the creation of an integrated, zero-emissions biorefinery that operates without generating waste or consuming freshwater and land. NEBULA will deliver sustainable solutions such as biodiesel from microbial lipids, omega-3 fatty acids for dairy enrichment, and biofertilizers fortified with bioactive compounds. The synergetic operation of these industrial units will lead to improved performance in technological, economic, environmental, and social dimensions, as validated through sustainability and life cycle assessments.
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

NTUA Proposal #6	
Call	European Regional Development Fund of the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH-INNOVATE (2021-2027)
Topic	Priority Area of the ESIF 2021-2027: Agri-food Chain Subcategory: 03.06.02 Sustainable Production & Proper Environmental Management
Type of Action	Intervention II: Partnerships between Businesses and Research Organizations
Proposal	
No	EKIIAP01-0066538
Title	Development of functional animal feeds from citrus by-products for the production of high nutritional value goat and sheep milk
Acronym	RumiFeed

NTUA Proposal #6	
Type*	Grant Budget-Based; 100%
Budget	~0.8 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission date	2 August 2024
Abstract	<p>The RumiFeed project tackles environmental challenges by converting citrus processing waste into functional feed additives for dairy goats and sheep. Citrus juice production generates large amounts of by-products that pose disposal and pollution problems. Simultaneously, increasing demand for animal products calls for sustainable feed solutions. Using green extraction, enzymatic hydrolysis, and encapsulation, RumiFeed will produce bioactive compounds and prebiotic oligosaccharides from citrus waste to enrich animal feed. These additives aim to improve milk yield and quality while reducing environmental impact. The project includes feeding trials to evaluate effects on milk composition and animal performance. RumiFeed promotes circular economy principles by transforming agro-industrial waste into valuable feed products, supporting sustainable livestock farming. It also fosters collaboration between research institutions and industry, advancing eco-friendly innovation in animal nutrition.</p>
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

4.5 Joint Proposals

Joint Proposal #1	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01 (EIC Pathfinder Challenges 2024)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101221903
Title	Development of Bio-based and biodegradable polyethylene and polyesters for food packaging and agricultural applications
Acronym	Bio2PEs
Type*	HORIZON Lump Sum Grant
Budget	~ 4 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	15 October 2024
TwInn4MicroUp partners	TUS & IMGGE & NTUA
Abstract	Bio2PEs aims to revolutionize the plastic sectors by developing bio-based and biodegradable polyethylene (PE) and polyester, directly derived from biomass waste, to combat plastic pollution and advance sustainability. The project will develop four eco-friendly, functional prototypes for food packaging, textile packaging, agricultural mulch, and crop protection membranes, addressing key sectors in need of sustainable alternatives. A crucial part of Bio2PEs is its comprehensive environmental, economic, and social impact assessment, covering the entire lifecycle of the materials. Biodegradability in open environments, with ecotoxicity tests will be carried out across four EU climate zones (including soil, freshwater, and marine environments), ensuring the materials meet real-world environmental requirements. To support circularity, Bio2PEs will develop

Joint Proposal #1	
	<p>a cellulose-based self-repairing coating to fix scratches, enhance the durability and reusability and significantly improve product lifespan. Bio2PEs will also enhance the recyclability of materials by quantifying the exact content of the recycled material through a fluorescence marker technology. The project will also leverage collaboration with other EU-funded projects, building on social studies of consumer behavior to design interactive labelling that encourages the adoption of biodegradable materials. Material development data will be shared with an AI tool, developed by a sister project, to expand the data pool and refine material development and biodegradability predictions. This project will support the European Circular Economy Action Plan by fostering scalable, sustainable solutions that reduce waste and plastic pollution while promoting resource efficiency.</p>
Result	Funded

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

Joint Proposal #2	
Call	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-DN-01 (MSCA Doctoral Networks 2024)
Topic	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-DN-01-01
Type of Action	HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-DN
Proposal	
No	101227428
Title	Empowering Innovation for a Sustainable Plastic Future
Acronym	SkillCirc
Type*	HORIZON Unit Grant
Budget	~ 2.8 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission Date	27 November 2024

Joint Proposal #2	
Twinn4MicroUp partners	TUS & IMGGE & NTUA
Abstract	<p>The SkillCirc Doctoral Network addresses the critical challenge of transitioning from a linear plastic economy to a circular, sustainable paradigm by advancing eco-plastic technologies and fostering interdisciplinary research. This initiative brings together a multidisciplinary consortium of leading academic and industry partners to train the next generation of researchers capable of driving innovation in plastic reuse, recycling, and sustainability. SkillCirc will train 11 Doctoral Candidates through a holistic program combining rigorous scientific research, hands-on laboratory experience, and engagement with industry and policy actors. Each DC will tackle a critical aspect of the plastic life cycle, from the development of bio-based and indefinitely recyclable polymers to the integration of artificial intelligence for real-time process monitoring and optimization. Innovative approaches such as biocoloring, biocatalytic depolymerization, and eco-polymer film development will pave the way for high-performance, sustainable alternatives to plastics. Alongside technical advancements, SkillCirc will explore the social, economic, and policy dimensions of plastic use, including public attitudes, household practices, and policy narratives, ensuring that innovations are socially embedded and widely adopted. The program employs advanced training methodologies, including interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches, to equip DCs with a diverse skill set. Reflective practice, structured industry placements, and exposure to social scientific perspectives will prepare researchers to bridge the gap between laboratory discoveries and real-world applications. Through collaboration, innovation, and a strong commitment to sustainability, SkillCirc aims to not only revolutionize the lifecycle of plastics but also cultivate the next generation of leaders who will drive transformative change in academia,</p>

Joint Proposal #2	
	industry, and policy making, shaping a greener, more sustainable future. Material development data will be shared with an AI tool, developed by a sister project, to expand the data pool and refine material development and biodegradability predictions. This project will support the European Circular Economy Action Plan by fostering scalable, sustainable solutions that reduce waste and plastic pollution while promoting resource efficiency.
Result	Not Funded (87.8%)

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

Joint Proposal #3	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN (EIC Pathfinder 2025)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101258885
Title	Reinventing electrolysis towards low-energy hybrid production of hydrogen and value-added chemicals
Acronym	RELEAD
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	~ 2.2 m EUR
Duration	48 months
Submission date	21 May 2025
TwInn4MicroUp partners	NTUA & IMGGE
Abstract	RELEAD's vision is to enable a future where electrolysis is no longer a costly approach, but a ubiquitous robust technology producing H ₂ and fine chemicals at scale. To this end, a radically new, low-energy electrolysis

Joint Proposal #3	
	<p>platform is proposed that will not only render H₂ economically viable and accessible but also unlock the simultaneous generation of a broad range of high-value chemicals essential for industry. This breakthrough will enable decentralized, large-scale H₂ generation with substantially reduced energy costs, allowing for the integration of H₂ into a broader clean energy ecosystem. By optimizing the electrolysis process to co-produce chemicals alongside H₂ at a reduced energy penalty, we create a circular and efficient system that provides economic value beyond H₂ alone, while supporting chemical industries on their transition to cleaner, more sustainable processes without sacrificing productivity or cost-effectiveness. This offers a pathway to not only decarbonize hard-to-abate sectors but also create a closed-loop economy, where renewable energy sources power the synthesis of industrially attractive chemicals without the use of fossil-based raw materials.</p>
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

Joint Proposal #4	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN (EIC Pathfinder 2025)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101257827
Title	Biorefining waste for sustainable integration of entwined biopolymers for advanced functionality
Acronym	EnTwine
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	~2.9 m EUR

Joint Proposal #4	
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	21 May 2025
TwInn4MicroUp partners	IMGGE & NTUA & TUS
Abstract	<p>EnTwine introduces a revolutionary approach to flexible biomaterial engineering inspired by the co-evolution of spider webs, which have served as models for high-performance, lightweight designs in various fields but remain underexplored in packaging. Our goal is to create PHA/BNC biomaterials as cost-effective, efficient alternatives to fossil-based plastics in food packaging and agriculture. By simplifying production and utilizing lignocellulosic waste, we aim to deliver biodegradable, high-performance materials with minimal environmental impact. Our materials will incorporate PHA intertwined with BNC scaffolds, mimicking the strength and flexibility of spider webs. This BNC framework will also carry selected bio-additives to enhance performance, producing biodegradable, antimicrobial food packaging with improved barrier properties and color indicators for food freshness. Additionally, we will create biodegradable agricultural mulches featuring temperature-responsive materials for optimized energy conversion. To promote sustainability, we will embed natural magnetosomes in our products to facilitate separation for (up)recycling. EnTwine’s processes will cover the entire lifecycle, from material design and production to maximizing durability and biodegradability. We will partner with SMEs to rigorously test biodegradability and functional performance, complemented by a comprehensive life cycle assessment and economic analysis. Ultimately, EnTwine aims to provide eco-innovative solutions that enhance resource efficiency, add value, and ensure safe biodegradation, shaping the future of sustainable manufacturing in the food and agricultural sectors.</p>
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

Joint Proposal #5	
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN (EIC Pathfinder 2025)
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN
Type of Action	HORIZON-EIC (HORIZON EIC Grants)
Proposal	
No	101257932
Title	Circular and Clean Solutions for Sustainable Management of Colored/Mixed Textile Waste and Wastewater in the Textile Industry
Acronym	CirCLEAN-TEX
Type*	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based
Budget	~ 3 m EUR
Duration	36 months
Submission Date	21 May 2025
TwInn4MicroUp partners	TUS & IMGGE
Abstract	<p>The textile industry is a major contributor to today’s global environmental crisis, generating millions of tonnes of waste annually, consuming vast quantities of freshwater, and serving as one of the largest sources of microplastic pollution. Additionally, colored polyester-cotton blends dominate the market but are notoriously difficult to recycle, while textile wastewater often contains hazardous substances, all of which pose serious risks to aquatic ecosystems and human health. Moreover, biopolymer production plays a critical role in the transition to a sustainable, circular economy by offering biodegradable and bio-based alternatives to conventional petroleum-derived plastics. In response, the interconnected and well-designed structure of CirCLEAN-TEX introduces a pioneering approach built on three mutually reinforcing pillars aimed at enabling circularity, sustainability, and zero waste by starting in the textile sector.</p> <p>- Solvent-Free Mechanochemical Recycling & Decolorization: Targeting non-recyclable blended and dyed textiles, this pillar introduces a novel, dry,</p>

Joint Proposal #5	
	<p>and scalable REX-based depolymerization process to recover high purity monomers, while separating cotton and residual fractions for further valorisation. Simultaneously, supercritical CO₂-based decolorization offers a clean pathway for textile reuse, ensuring fiber integrity without water or harmful chemicals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-Performance Wastewater Treatment: Addressing the water crisis and textile effluent pollution, this pillar focuses on the design of next-generation filtration systems capable of selectively rejecting micro/nanoplastics, dyes, and PFAS, resulting in closed-loop water reuse and point-of-source treatment. • Biopolymer Production from Residual Streams: Ensuring a zero-waste approach, all non-reusable or degraded fractions, including carbonized cotton and extracted pollutants, are valorised through advanced bioengineering processes into high-performance biopolymers.
Result	Pending

* *Type of Model Grant Agreement*

5. The TwInn4MicroUp Patenting Strategy

5.1 General Exploitation plan

One of the aims of the TwInn4MicroUp project is to develop microbial cell factories that can produce valuable biopigments from plastic waste. By leveraging advances in molecular techniques, the project will identify and engineer microbial strains capable of converting plastic waste monomers into bioactive compounds. This innovative approach not only addresses plastic waste management but also contributes to environmental and economic sustainability through the creation of high value bioproducts. The potential commercial value of such a process and the possible intellectual property (IP) protection strategy needs to be developed. Hence, during the

timeframe of the project, we will explore key and potentially patentable technologies but also learn how to conduct a comprehensive IP Rights (IPR) assessment.

IP assessment must be implemented upon a solid understanding of IPR —their establishment, management, protection and exploitation. Usually, a methodological framework for IPR needs to be formulated, concerning the identification of IPR that can be established, critical decisions and management challenges, specific points on different kinds of IPR (patents, other industrial IPR, copyright, know-how and trade secrets), ways of protecting IP, as well as possible paths for its exploitation.

IP refers to original creations of the human mind, recognized and protected by law as intangible assets. These creations, while they may take tangible forms (such as prototypes or artworks), derive their value from the underlying idea or human creativity. National legislation specifies which types of IP qualify for protection, the procedures for their establishment, and the terms of ownership. International treaties extend this framework by regulating cross-border recognition and protection. There are two primary categories of IPR:

 Industrial Property Rights, which protect creations with industrial or commercial applications, such as patents, (industrial) designs, trademarks and utility models. These rights require formal registration.

 Copyright, which protects artistic, literary, scientific, and digital creations, such as software and algorithms. Unlike industrial property rights, copyright is automatically granted upon creation without requiring registration.

Despite their differences, IPR share certain common characteristics:

- They grant exclusive rights to use, exploit, and enforce protection.
- They enable enforcement through judicial systems to prevent unauthorized use.
- Their validity is restricted to the jurisdiction of the granting country unless extended via international treaties.

National legislation plays a pivotal role in the establishment of IPR. It defines the types of IPR recognized, the procedures for their registration or establishment, ownership terms (including joint ownership), and the scope of rights granted, such as exclusive use, exploitation, and enforcement. However, these rights are jurisdiction-specific, and cross-border protection relies on international

treaties, such as the Patent Cooperation Treaty and the Berne Convention. These treaties do not automatically provide global recognition but facilitate protection and registration across multiple countries. Additionally, EU treaties offer unitary rights, such as the EU Trademark and Unitary Patent, recognized throughout EU member states. Determining the "nationality" of an IPR, that is, identifying the applicable jurisdiction and legislation, can depend on various factors, such as the location of creation, the creator's residence, or the employing organization's country of establishment. These criteria are typically guided by national laws and international treaties and will be explored for educational but also for practical reasons in the context of the research that is undertaken in this project.

We will explore – but also learn how to explore - all potential IPR types that could be related to Twinn4MicroUp. Based on the KERs that have been identified in previous steps (see *Deliverable D6.1*), the development of an innovative approach for upcycling recovered plastic monomers, deriving from green bio/mechano/chemical technologies, into valuable bio-pigments through the power of engineered microbes, could be further explored for potential IP protection.

5.1.1 Patents

A patent is an IPR that grants the owner exclusive rights to an invention for up to 20 years. It allows the patent holder to prevent others from using, selling, or making the invention within the specified jurisdictions where it is filed. Patents are territorial, meaning they are only enforceable in jurisdictions where they are filed —something that also affects their commercialization potential. Selecting the jurisdiction involves choosing the applicable national legislation, which determines patentability and rights conferred. The types of patents with respect to jurisdictions are:

- **National Patent:** Protection is granted by a national authority and applies only in that specific country.
- **Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT):** Streamlines the process of filing a single application for multiple countries, though individual national registrations are required.
- **EU Unitary Patent:** From June 2023, allows a single application to cover up to 17 EU countries.
- **Cross-national Registries:** Applications via the European Patent Office (EPO) require further national registrations to make the patent enforceable.

Patents confer rights to prevent unauthorized use, manufacture, or sale of an invention within the jurisdictions where they are granted, with some exceptions for non-commercial purposes, such as academic research. These rights can be sold, licensed, or assigned.

An integral aspect of the patent process is publicity, requiring disclosure of the invention to ensure knowledge sharing, transparency, and innovation. This dissemination allows others to build on existing advancements while holding inventors accountable.

In order to be patentable, an invention must meet specific criteria, namely:

- *Novelty*: Not being previously known or published.
- *Non-obviousness*: Not being easily conceived by experts in the field.
- *Utility*: Having practical applications.

European countries also require the invention to show scientific advancement. As regards ownership, the patent applicant is usually the prospective owner, who may be different from the inventor (for example, Universities often retain ownership of patents created by their researchers).

In collaborative research, co-ownership may also apply, if contributions are inseparable.

Of course, a patent application is usually a complex and time-consuming process, depending on the specific characteristics of the invention and the jurisdiction of filing among other factors. The possibility of opposition from competitors or other parties can further perplex the process. That said, employing the expertise of a patent attorney is usually the safest path to a patent application, although this might not be necessary in this project.

5.1.2 Other Industrial Property Rights

Besides patents, two other types —designs and trademarks— are widely established and recognized in almost all legal systems. The former protecting the visual design of products intended for industrial or commercial use and the latter protecting brand names, logos, and symbols. They both could have some value for Twinn4MicroUp. However, such Industrial Property Rights are specific to certain jurisdictions. For instance, utility models, which protect technical solutions to practical problems or minor improvements to existing products, are available in some countries as an alternative to patents with less stringent requirements for inventiveness and simpler, faster procedures for examination and registration. Similarly, new plant varieties developed through human intervention, such as laboratory or agricultural practices, and

geographical indications, which protect the origin of certain products (often agricultural or tied to cultural heritage), are recognized only in specific legal contexts.

Additionally, some jurisdictions extend the definition of IPR to include original scientific or technical knowledge, known as “Know-How,” and confidential business or technical information, referred to as “Trade Secrets.” These also could be used in the context of Twinn4MicroUp.

Furthermore, in certain cases, countries introduce specialized IPRs tailored to protect unique innovations with significant applications. For example, the European Union established specific rights for semiconductor topographies through legislation, recognizing their specialized nature. International treaties often facilitate mutual recognition of Industrial Property Rights across jurisdictions, defining how creations protected in one country may be protected in another one. This may involve applying similar Industrial Property Rights protections, copyright laws, contracts, or even rules on unfair competition.

5.1.3 Copyright

Copyright is an IPR that protects unique creations of significant creativity in art, science, craft, and technology. Unlike other IPR, copyright does not require the creation to have industrial or commercial applications. Instead, it protects the work for its originality and creativity. Copyright is established automatically upon the creation’s completion (“birth”), without requiring formal registration, as long as the author’s identity and the time of creation can be proven with evidence, such as a timestamped publication or certification by a public authority. The creator initially owns the copyright but may transfer it to another entity, such as an organization or company.

Copyright covers a wide range of human creations, including artistic works (literature, music, and visual arts), scientific studies and methods, and digital technology such as algorithms, software, and databases. In some cases, and in certain jurisdictions, copyright may also extend to practical knowledge or “know-how” with potential applications. Special rules apply to specific types of copyrightable work, such as software and databases, to define the subject matter more precisely. Copyright can also coexist with industrial property rights, such as patents, creating challenges in managing overlapping protections. The logos and work that is being developed in the hub might also be protected through copyrights and trademarks.

5.2 IPR Strategy and Management

Managing IPR involves several critical strategic challenges, requiring careful planning and decision-making. To begin with, the value of IPR depends on their novelty and distinctiveness. For registered IPRs, such as patents and designs, uniqueness must be proven during the registration process and gains formal recognition upon approval. For non-registrable IPRs like copyright, uniqueness must be demonstrated continuously, particularly during exploitation or enforcement. Another significant aspect concerns ownership, as it involves defining, allocating, or transferring rights. This also includes determining whether the creator retains ownership and how ownership is distributed in collaborative projects. Apparently, ownership decisions impact the management and economic utilization of the IP asset.

Territorial scope presents a further challenge, concerning where IPRs should be protected and commercialized. Decisions about national versus international exploitation affect procedures and costs, and selecting target countries requires market analysis to justify their strategic importance. Moreover, exploitation and commercialization require identifying the best methods for utilizing IPRs, such as licensing, transfer, direct commercialization, or collaborations. Responsibility for commercialization must also be determined, with the pertinent options including industry-led exploitation through licensing, co-development, or open innovation, or owner-led initiatives like spinouts or university tech-transfer entities. Effective exploitation requires defining the scope of use, including its duration, exclusivity, and geographical reach.

From both an exploitation and a protection perspective, as economic assets, IPRs require a valuation process to determine their financial worth. As regards commercialization, value influences revenue, and as far as protection is concerned, value underpins compensation in cases of infringement. Valuation methods vary and are based on specific models tailored to the unique nature of intellectual property. In any case, IPR valuation is a challenging task, including reliance on assumptions, negotiations, and expert input. Members of the NTUA Technology Transfer office may support this process in the context of this project as well

A fairly common yet complex situation arises when ownership and management of IP are created collaboratively. Co-creators must determine whether ownership will be joint or assigned to one individual, and for university-assigned IP, the moral and economic rights of contributors must be clearly defined, including mechanisms for revenue sharing. In cases of joint ownership, co-owners need to agree on their respective shares, as these affect both revenue distribution and governance.

Effective management also requires clear decision-making rules. Furthermore, in collaborative projects, it is important to distinguish the primary creator or inventor from those whose contributions were supportive but not critical. Related concepts have been agreed among all consortium members through the signed Consortium Agreement.

Often, co-existing IPRs on a single innovation also introduce complexities in prioritization. Research and innovation generate multiple forms of IP, each eligible for different IPR. Thus, strategic decisions need to be made, focusing on which IPRs offer the highest potential for commercialization or require active protection, particularly for non-registered rights like copyright.

As regards protection and enforcement of IPRs, proactive and reactive strategies are required to safeguard their value. Preventive measures, such as confidentiality agreements and policies, help in this aspect by maintaining uniqueness. In addition, regular monitoring is essential to detect potential infringements, while enforcement actions, such as judicial proceedings or forced licensing, address violations. Selecting the right professionals and tools to support protection efforts is critical, as is managing the significant costs associated with monitoring, preventive measures, and enforcement actions.

5.2.1 IPR Protection

IP protection is vital for preserving the uniqueness and value of creations and inventions. It ensures that the owner retains exclusive rights to use, (re)produce and commercialize their work, and that the economic value of intellectual assets is maintained. However, these rights can be threatened by unauthorized use, copying, or misuse of the IP, all of which constitute infringements, thus rendering the effective IP protection essential.

IP protection involves both preventive and remedial measures. Preventive actions include legal and technological measures. Legal measures often involve embedding obligations in contracts with collaborators or personnel and establishing university regulations that outline penalties for unauthorized use or misuse of IP. Technological measures, such as access restrictions and emerging tools like blockchain, enhance security by preventing unauthorized access, use, and reproduction. Confidentiality is also crucial, particularly for registrable IP like patents, where

secrecy ensures uniqueness before formal rights are established. We do not feel that we need to follow such measures in the context of this project

Finally, a key aspect of IP protection is securing the moral rights of creators. This involves recognizing and publicly acknowledging the creator or inventor, irrespective of ownership, and protecting their reputation from harm caused by misuse or slander. This ensures the moral value of the IP is upheld alongside its commercial utility.

5.2.2 IPR Exploitation

IPR can generate income for their owner through commercial exploitation, which can be achieved in three primary ways, which will be explored in the context of this project: (i) spin out, (ii) IP licensing, and (iii) IP transfer, especially for parts of KER 3, the innovative approach for upcycling recovered plastic monomers, deriving from green bio/mechano/chemical technologies, into valuable bio-pigments through engineered microbes.

Spin Out

A spin out is a strategic approach to exploiting intellectual property (IP) by creating an independent company to commercialize inventions or creations. It involves transforming IP into tangible products or services, such as producing a patented product, integrating a protected design, or trading under a trademarked logo. For universities, spinouts enable commercialization without violating their non-commercial mission, providing a pathway to bring research innovations to market. Spin outs are ideal in cases where the IP has clear commercial potential, requires focused development, or can attract external investment. They allow researchers and universities to generate revenue through either equity or licensing, contribute to economic growth, and enhance institutional reputation. Moreover, spinouts create opportunities for collaboration with industry and expand access to markets.

While spin outs offer significant benefits, they also pose challenges, including the need for substantial resources, market uncertainties, and complex IP management. Universities play a key role in supporting spinouts through incubation services, funding, and business development assistance, while retaining equity or licensing rights to benefit from future returns. In any case,

careful planning is essential, involving market readiness assessments, stakeholder alignment, and sustainable business models.

IP Licensing

Licensing allows IP owners to generate revenue by granting others the right to use, materialize, or commercialize their creations. It is particularly suited for non-commercial entities, such as universities, where direct commercialization of inventions or creations is typically not feasible. Alongside spinouts and IP sales, licensing represents one of the primary ways to exploit intellectual property, offering flexibility and retaining ownership of the asset. Licensing involves granting specific permissions for defined purposes. Licensing specifies the scope of use, which can include technological applications, commercial sectors, or integration into larger systems. Licensing agreements also define the duration, territorial scope, exclusivity, and financial terms, such as lump-sum payments or royalties. Additionally, responsibilities for IP protection and enforcement are outlined to prevent unauthorized use and ensure compliance.

IP Transfer

IP Transfer means transferring ownership to another party. It is particularly beneficial when the transfer occurs at a price that reflects the market value of the asset, as determined through a rigorous evaluation process, or when it provides financial or strategic benefits, such as contributing to a commercial venture or supporting joint development projects that may generate higher-value intellectual property. Transfers can be executed as standalone transactions or as part of more complex agreements, such as co-development or joint research collaborations. The valuation of IP for transfer differs from that for licensing. While licensing focuses on the specific terms of use, such as exclusivity, application, and geographical scope, IP transfer considers the asset's overall value, including its current worth and future potential revenues.

IP transfer offers several advantages, the first being that it can generate immediate revenue. Furthermore, it allows risk sharing, by shifting the commercialization burden to an external party, that possesses the resources and expertise to bring the product or service to market. Additionally, transferring IP to an organization with established access to markets can open new opportunities for commercializing other developed IP or spinout ventures, benefiting from the transferee's distribution channels and customer base. However, a major shortcoming of this option is that, once

the IP is transferred, the original owner loses ownership and associated rights, and, to continue using the transferred IP for research or derivative works, a license to ensure freedom-to-operate needs to be negotiated.

6. Patent Application Trainings

6.1 Performed Trainings

6.1.1 NTUA partner

The NTUA Technology Transfer Office (headed by Professor Aggelos Tsakanikas, member of the NTUA project partner) organized a specialized 3-hour workshop, together with the Hellenic Industrial Property Academy, with the aim of enhancing researchers' skills for analysing technological information available in patents.

Training title: **Role of patent literature as a bibliographic source of technological information⁹**

Organiser: NTUA Technology Transfer Office & Hellenic Industrial Property Academy

Date: 27th May 2025

Location: NTUA campus

Consortium Participant(s): Evangelos Topakas, Christina Ferousi, Efstratios Nikolaiivits

The seminar focused on the role of patent literature as a source of technological information. The main session addressed two core topics: the evaluation of inventions in terms of novelty, inventive step, and industrial applicability based on existing public knowledge and technical standards; and methods for retrieving scientific and technological insights from patent documents, with a hands-on analysis of patents in the field of climate change mitigation and adaptation technologies (CPC code Y02). The seminar combined theoretical insights with interactive exploration of patent data to highlight its value in tracking technological progress. Key speakers included:

⁹ <https://tto.ntua.gr/ergastirio-i-symvoli-ton-diplomaton-eyresitechnias-os-vivliografikis-pigis-patent-literature-technologikis-pliroforisis-2/>

- 🏛️ Prof. Angelos Tsakanikas; Prof. of Economic Evaluation of Technology, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship Systems, Director of the Laboratory of Industrial and Energy Economics (NTUA), Director of the Technology Transfer Office (NTUA)
- 🏛️ Panagiotis Kanellopoulos; General Director, Hellenic Industrial Property Organisation
- 🏛️ Dr. Lambros Pyrgiotis; Member of the Board of Directors of the Hellenic Industrial Property Organisation and the Hellenic Academy of Industrial Property
- 🏛️ Loudovikos Vanerk; Head of the ICT Inventions Department of the Hellenic Industrial Property Organisation, member of the Hellenic Academy of Industrial Property

Figure 10. Material from the “Role of patent literature as a bibliographic source of technological information” (NTUA partner; Training No2).

6.1.2 IMGGE partner

A Sector for Technology transfer¹⁰ has been established at the IMGGE partner institution in 2016, with the aim to support and assist researchers throughout the entire technology transfer process. This sector oversees technology transfer and various aspects of research commercialization at IMGGE, while also fostering connections between IMGGE and the industry. Dr Jelena Milovanovic is part of this IMGGE Sector and has attended the following training:

Training title: Patent System and Intellectual Property Protection

Organiser: Intellectual Property Office of the Republic of Serbia

Dates: 21st February 2025 and 12th March 2025

¹⁰ <https://imgge.bg.ac.rs/en/about-us/organisation/sector-for-technology-transfer>

Location: online

Consortium Participant(s): Jelena Milovanović

As part of the TwInn4MicroUp project's focus on innovation management and intellectual property (IP) awareness, two specialised workshops on patent writing and protection were attended by members of IMGGE's Transfer Technology Sector. Among the participants was Jelena Milovanović, also a core member of the TwInn4MicroUp team, contributing to the project's innovation and commercialization strategies.

The first workshop, titled ***Introduction to the Patent System***, was held on the 21st of February 2025 and led by MSc Jelena Tešić from The Intellectual Property Office of the Republic of Serbia. This training provided a structured introduction to the fundamentals of patent protection, covering patentable subject matter and criteria for patentability, core components of a patent application, filing rights and procedures at national and international levels, overview of international systems (WIPO, EPO, and PCT) and introduction to utility models (small patents). A total of 23 participants attended this session.

The second workshop, ***Patent Protection for Innovative Technical Solutions***, was held on the 12th of March 2025 and delivered by Nataša Milovanovic from The Intellectual Property Office of the Republic of Serbia. This session focused on: The legal foundations and strategic importance of patent protection, procedures for securing national patents and small patents (utility models), key elements of Serbian IP legislation, including the Patent Law and Rulebook on Public Registers and Patent Applications (Official Gazette RS No. 99/11, 113/17, 95/18, 66/19, and 123/21). A total of 18 participants took part in the session. Both workshops significantly enhanced participants' understanding of intellectual property frameworks and improved their capacity to support innovation and technology transfer activities within the context of Horizon Europe projects.

Figure 11. Material from the “Patent System and Intellectual Property Protection” (IMGGE partner; Training No5).

6.2. Planned Trainings

Based on the above-mentioned experience and knowledge, the IMGGE partner will organize a dedicated workshop for the consortium within Year 2 of the TwInn4MicroUp project. This workshop will be designed to transfer essential knowledge on intellectual property assessment, compliance with patent laws, and the development of clear patent claims and comprehensive patent descriptions. Additionally, these activities will be enriched by the active involvement of TUS experts, who will contribute their specialized experience in research management and innovation. By combining the strengths of both IMGGE and TUS, the project ensures that NTUA staff receive well-rounded, practical training that addresses both the technical and administrative aspects of patenting. This collaborative effort will significantly enhance NTUA’s capabilities in protecting and leveraging its research outputs throughout the project and beyond.

Furthermore, NTUA plans to organise, within Year 2, an educational seminar on the use of Patsnap¹¹. Patsnap is a leading patent analysis tool, which includes a wide range of data was collected to analyse existing intellectual property. This analysis focused on identifying relevant patents, key patent holders, geographic trends, and current legal statuses, facilitating the

¹¹ <https://www.patsnap.com/>

identification of freedom-to-operate (FTO) opportunities and patentability potential. Key elements of Patsnap include:

- Defining technology descriptions and selecting relevant keywords and phrases to guide targeted patent searches
- Filtering search results by semantic relevance, citation count, and legal status to detect influential patents
- Analysing geographic trends in patent filings and identifying active players in the relevant fields
- Reviewing the top-ranked patents to assess their novelty, relevance to the examined technologies, as well as possible implications for FTO.